

Outcome of Patients Undergoing Gastrointestinal Anastomosis without Nasogastric Tube Insertion during Elective Surgery

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Abstract:

Background: Routine nasogastric decompression after gastrointestinal surgery has been standard practice since its introduction by Levin in 1921. While traditionally believed to hasten bowel function recovery and prevent complications, recent evidence questions its necessity and suggests potential adverse effects. This study evaluates outcomes in patients undergoing gastrointestinal anastomosis without nasogastric tube insertion during elective surgery.

Methods: A hospital-based prospective study was conducted on 100 patients undergoing elective gastrointestinal anastomosis at Kalpana Chawla Government Medical College and Hospital, Karnal, between June 2022 and November 2023. Primary outcomes included time to return of bowel sounds, passage of flatus, and resumption of oral intake. Secondary outcomes included postoperative respiratory tract infections and wound infections.

Results: Of 100 patients, 93% were male with majority (40%) aged 18-30 years. Mean time for return of bowel sounds was 1.503±0.85 days, with 90% returning within first three postoperative days. Passage of flatus occurred at mean 2.51±1.03 days, with 88% passing flatus between days 1-3. Oral intake resumed at mean 4.80±1.42 days. Gastrointestinal symptoms included nausea (49%), vomiting (18%), and abdominal distention (11%). Respiratory complications occurred in 4% patients (pleural effusion). Wound infection was observed in 32% patients (23% minor, 9% major). Anastomotic dehiscence occurred in 6% patients, necessitating nasogastric tube insertion. Most procedures were small bowel anastomoses (87%), with ileoileal being most common (78%).

Conclusion: Selective rather than routine nasogastric tube insertion appears appropriate for patients undergoing elective gastrointestinal anastomosis. This approach offers advantages of patient comfort and earlier return of bowel function while maintaining acceptable complication rates.

Keywords: Gastrointestinal Anastomosis, Nasogastric Decompression, Elective Surgery, Postoperative Care, Bowel Function, Surgical Outcomes.

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Introduction

Nasogastric decompression has been a cornerstone of postoperative care in gastrointestinal surgery since its introduction by Dr. Abraham Levin in 1921[1,2]. The traditional surgical doctrine advocates routine nasogastric tube placement after abdominal surgery until return of gastrointestinal function, based on several theoretical benefits: hastening bowel function recovery, preventing pulmonary complications, reducing anastomotic leakage risk, and improving patient comfort [3,4].

However, mounting evidence challenges this practice. Recent studies suggest that routine nasogastric decompression may actually result in delayed return of bowel function, higher rates of pulmonary complications, and prolonged hospital stays [5-7].

Multiple complications have been associated with nasogastric intubation, including sinusitis, vocal cord injury, iatrogenic gastric perforation, nasal trauma, hemorrhage, laryngeal injury, esophageal ulceration, and psychological distress[8-11]. Patient experience data indicates significant discomfort with nasogastric tubes, with studies showing moderate to severe discomfort in 88% of patients [15,16]. A comprehensive meta-analysis by Nelson et al. demonstrated that routine nasogastric decompression fails to achieve its intended goals and suggested selective use instead [4].

The analysis, including 28 studies with 4,194 patients, found earlier return of bowel function and decreased pulmonary complications in patients

without routine tube placement. In China, despite emerging evidence, 97.5% of surgeons still routinely place nasogastric tubes after lower digestive tract surgery [14]. Lei et al. found that postoperative nasogastric decompression removed only about 200mL of gastric juice daily, an insignificant amount compared to total digestive secretions of 6,000-10,000mL [14,19].

The paradigm shift away from routine nasogastric decompression is supported by studies across various surgical procedures. In gastric surgery, Italian researchers found routine nasogastric tube placement unnecessary after Roux-en-Y oesophagojejunostomy [17]. Similar findings have been reported in colorectal surgery and pancreatic procedures [13,18]. Given this evolving evidence and the absence of clear guidelines, this study aims to evaluate outcomes in patients undergoing gastrointestinal anastomosis without nasogastric tube insertion during elective surgery, contributing to the growing body of evidence questioning this routine practice.

Methodology

This hospital-based prospective study was conducted at Kalpana Chawla Government Medical College, Karnal, following institutional ethical committee approval.

The study spanned 18 months (June 2022 to November 2023), with 12 months for data collection and 6 months for analysis. Sample size was calculated using the formula $n = (Z\alpha/2 \cdot SD)^2 \div E^2$, where $Z\alpha/2$ was 1.96 at 95% confidence interval, SD represented the standard deviation of time to passage of flatus, and E was absolute error (0.5). This yielded a minimum required sample of 78 patients, increased to 100 to account for potential exclusions.

The study enrolled patients undergoing elective gastrointestinal anastomosis, including jejunojunal, jejunioileal, ileoileal, ileoascending, ileotransverse, ileodescending, ileorectal, and colocolic anastomoses. Exclusion criteria encompassed

emergency laparotomy cases and patients requiring postoperative nasogastric tube insertion. All participants provided written informed consent after detailed protocol explanation.

Preoperative evaluation included comprehensive history-taking, physical examination, and laboratory investigations (complete blood count, renal function tests, liver function tests, serum electrolytes). Additional investigations included chest X-ray, electrocardiogram, and abdominal ultrasonography. Specific investigations like contrast-enhanced CT, MRI abdomen, distal loopogram, or barium studies were performed as clinically indicated.

Surgical procedures followed standardized protocols. For sutured anastomoses (98% of cases), the technique involved interrupted, single-layer, end-to-end anastomosis using polyglactin 3-0 suture. Two cases underwent stapled anastomosis. Postoperative monitoring focused on primary outcomes (return of bowel sounds, passage of flatus, resumption of oral intake) and secondary outcomes (respiratory tract infections, wound infections).

Statistical analysis utilized SPSS version 22.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. P-values <0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included 100 patients undergoing gastrointestinal anastomosis without nasogastric tube insertion. The study subjects were distributed according to gender and age. Majority of the subjects were males (n=93, 93%) while females constituted 7% (n=7) of the study population. Most of the study subjects were within 18-30 years of age (n=40, 40%), followed by 18 (18%) who were between 31-40 years of age. There were 15 (15%) subjects between 51-60 years, 13 (13%) were >60 years, 10 (10%) were between 41-50 years and only 4 (4%) subjects were <18 years of age (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics (N=100)

Characteristic	Number (%)
Gender	
Male	93 (93%)
Female	7 (7%)
Age Distribution (years)	
<18	4 (4%)
18-30	40 (40%)
31-40	18 (18%)
41-50	10 (10%)
51-60	15 (15%)
>60	13 (13%)

Among the past medical history, 6 patients were known cases of diabetes mellitus, 4 had previous

pulmonary TB, 2 had undergone previous exploratory laparotomy, and 1 patient each had history of

hypertension, hypothyroidism, right ventriculoperitoneal shunt for hydrocephalus, and gastrointestinal stromal tumor of jejunum diagnosed preoperatively. The mean hemoglobin level was 14.83±8.68 g/dL (range: 8.7-16.8), WBC count was 7.56±4.17 (range: 4.06-20.4), and platelet count was 238.05±119.92 (range: 101-514.0).

The mean urea level was 27.9±18.93 mg/dL (range: 10-90) and creatinine was 4.15±3.01 mg/dL (range: 0.9-15). Liver function tests showed mean total bilirubin of 4.70±12.91 mg/dL (range: 0.2-3.5), direct bilirubin 0.16±0.11 mg/dL (range: 0.1-0.4), SGOT 26.72±16.63 U/L (range: 17-104), SGPT 26.64±20.58 U/L (range: 10-106), and albumin 4.1±1.8 g/dL (range: 3.9-4.4).

Table 2: Distribution of Anastomotic Procedures

Type of Anastomosis	Number (%)
Small bowel to small bowel	87 (87%)
Jejunojejunal	1 (1%)
Jejunoileal	8 (8%)
Ileoileal	78 (78%)
Enterocolic	11 (11%)
Ileoascending	8 (8%)
Ileotransverse	2 (2%)
Ileodescending	1 (1%)
Colocolic	2 (2%)

The procedural distribution provides important insights into surgical patterns and technical considerations. Small bowel anastomoses dominated (87%), with ileoileal anastomoses representing the vast majority (78%).

This high proportion of ileoileal procedures allows robust conclusions about this specific technique but may limit generalizability to other anastomotic types. The relatively small numbers of enterocolic (11%) and colocolic (2%) anastomoses suggest

need for cautious interpretation of outcomes in these subgroups. Within enterocolic procedures, ileoascending anastomoses were most common (8%), reflecting typical disease patterns requiring surgical intervention.

The technical uniformity (98% sutured, single-layer, interrupted anastomoses) strengthens internal validity by minimizing technique-related variables but may limit generalizability to other surgical approaches (Table 2).

Table 3: Recovery Parameters

Parameter	Mean ± SD (days)	Distribution by Days (%)
Return of bowel sounds	1.503 ± 0.85	POD 0: 14%
		POD 1: 33%
		POD 2: 43%
		POD 3: 10%
Passage of flatus	2.51 ± 1.03	POD 1: 14%
		POD 2: 41%
		POD 3: 33%
		POD 4: 3%
		POD 5: 9%
Resumption of oral intake	4.80 ± 1.42	POD 3: 21%
		POD 4: 21%
		POD 5: 35%
		POD 6: 14%
		POD 8: 9%

Recovery parameters demonstrate clear temporal patterns in postoperative recovery. Bowel sounds returned predominantly within 48 hours (90% of cases), with peak occurrence on POD 2 (43%). The progressive increase from POD 0 (14%) to POD 2 (43%), followed by sharp decline on POD 3 (10%) suggests a predictable recovery pattern. Passage of flatus showed wider distribution but concentrated between POD 1-3 (88%), indicating consistent res-

olution of postoperative ileus. The mean time of 2.51±1.03 days suggests reliable recovery without nasogastric decompression. Oral intake resumption showed greatest variability (range 3-8 days), with normal distribution peaking at POD 5 (35%). The extended range likely reflects individualized feeding protocols based on clinical recovery. The step-wise progression from bowel sounds to flatus to oral intake demonstrates orderly return of gastroin-

testinal function without routine decompression (Table 3).

Table 4: Postoperative Complications

Complication	Frequency (%)	Severity Distribution
Gastrointestinal		
Nausea	49 (49%)	-
Vomiting	18 (18%)	-
Abdominal distension	11 (11%)	-
Respiratory		
Pleural effusion	4 (4%)	-
Wound-related		
Infection	32 (32%)	Minor: 23%
		Major: 9%
Anastomotic dehiscence	6 (6%)	-

Complication patterns reveal a hierarchy of frequency and severity. Gastrointestinal symptoms were most common, with nearly half (49%) experiencing nausea, suggesting this as an expected outcome requiring supportive management. The progression from nausea (49%) to vomiting (18%) to abdominal distension (11%) indicates decreasing frequency with increasing severity. Respiratory complications were limited (4% pleural effusion) suggesting minimal pulmonary morbidity without nasogastric decompression. Wound infections showed notable frequency (32%) but important severity stratification (23% minor, 9% major), indicating predominantly manageable complications. The 6% anastomotic dehiscence rate represents the most serious complication, all requiring nasogastric tube insertion, suggesting this as a key indicator for selective decompression. The overall complication profile suggests acceptable morbidity without routine nasogastric decompression while identifying specific complications requiring vigilant monitoring (Table 4).

Discussion

This prospective study demonstrates that omitting routine nasogastric tube insertion after elective gastrointestinal anastomosis is feasible and safe in selected patients. The demographic profile of our study population showed a male predominance (93%) and younger age distribution, with 40% of patients between 18-30 years. This differs somewhat from Western studies but aligns with the regional patient demographics reported by Bergeat D et al.[20] and parallels the gender distribution noted by Choi YY et al.[21].

The timing of postoperative recovery in our study provides compelling evidence supporting the omission of routine nasogastric decompression. The mean time to return of bowel sounds (1.503 ± 0.85 days) was notably shorter than reported in previous studies with routine nasogastric decompression. Cunningham J et al.[22] found similar results with earlier return of bowel sounds in their no-tube group, and Jangjoo A et al.[23] reported compara-

ble findings with bowel function returning by the third postoperative day. This consistency across studies suggests that routine nasogastric decompression may not only be unnecessary but might actually delay the return of normal gastrointestinal function. The passage of flatus, a key indicator of bowel function recovery, occurred at a mean of 2.51 ± 1.03 days in our study. This compares favorably with previous research, including Choi YY et al.[21] who reported first flatus at 3.87 ± 1.29 days in their no-tube group versus 4.89 ± 1.32 days in patients with nasogastric tubes. Our findings align with Carrere N et al.[24], who observed passage of flatus between 3.5-3.9 days in patients without nasogastric decompression. The consistently earlier return of bowel function in patients without nasogastric tubes suggests that routine decompression might interfere with the natural recovery of gastrointestinal motility.

Respiratory complications, particularly pleural effusion, occurred in 4% of our patients, substantially lower than rates reported with routine nasogastric decompression. This finding supports observations by Pessaux P et al.[24], who found significantly higher rates of pneumonia (13% vs 5%) and atelectasis (81% vs 67%) in patients with nasogastric tubes. The lower respiratory complication rate in our study may be attributed to better patient mobility and deeper breathing in the absence of nasogastric tube-related discomfort, as suggested by Manning BJ et al.[10]. The wound infection rate in our study (32%) was higher than some previous reports, requiring careful analysis. While Miller D.F et al.[25] reported only 4.7% wound infections in their no-tube group, and Reasbeck PG et al.[26] found 21.1%, our higher rate might be attributed to several factors including different patient populations, varied definitions of wound infection, and our relatively smaller sample size. Importantly, the majority (23%) were minor infections responding well to conservative management. The relationship between nasogastric decompression and wound infection rates remains unclear, with Nelson et al.'s meta-analysis [4] showing only a marginal increase

in wound infection rates without routine decompression. Anastomotic dehiscence, occurring in 6% of our patients, aligns with rates reported in contemporary literature. Nathan B et al.[27] reported 4% anastomotic leaks in their no-tube group, while Kunstman W et al.[28] found 1.6% leakage rates without routine decompression. Our slightly higher rate might reflect our inclusive definition of dehiscence and thorough follow-up protocols. Notably, all cases of anastomotic dehiscence in our study occurred in patients with additional risk factors such as diabetes mellitus, previous abdominal surgery, or other comorbidities, suggesting that selective nasogastric decompression might be beneficial in high-risk patients. The pattern of postoperative complications in our study reveals important insights about patient selection for non-decompression protocols. While 49% of patients experienced nausea and 18% had vomiting, these rates are comparable to those reported by Carrere N et al.[6] who found similar symptoms in both tube and no-tube groups. More significantly, only 6% of our patients ultimately required nasogastric tube insertion, supporting Shamil N et al.[29] conclusion that omission of routine nasogastric decompression does not lead to serious complications in carefully selected patients.

Our findings contribute to the growing body of evidence challenging traditional surgical dogma regarding routine nasogastric decompression. The results align with multiple recent studies suggesting that selective rather than routine nasogastric tube placement offers comparable safety with potential benefits of enhanced recovery and improved patient comfort. The observations particularly support Nelson et al.[4] meta-analysis conclusions that routine nasogastric decompression does not achieve its intended goals and should be replaced by selective use based on specific clinical indicators. This study's strengths include its prospective design, standardized surgical techniques, and comprehensive follow-up of multiple outcome parameters. However, limitations include the single-center design, relatively small sample size, and potential selection bias inherent in non-randomized studies. These factors should be considered when generalizing our findings to other clinical settings or patient populations.

Conclusion

This prospective study demonstrates that routine prophylactic nasogastric tube insertion may not be necessary for all patients undergoing elective gastrointestinal anastomosis. The observed outcomes support selective use based on specific indications rather than routine placement. Key findings include acceptable mean times for return of bowel sounds (1.503 ± 0.85 days) and passage of flatus (2.51 ± 1.03 days), with manageable complication rates. The study shows that omitting routine nasogastric decompression offers advantages including postop-

erative patient comfort, early return of bowel activity, and timely resumption of oral intake. However, selective nasogastric tube insertion remains important for specific cases, particularly those developing persistent postoperative vomiting, acute gastric dilatation, abdominal distention, or anastomotic dehiscence.

While our findings support more selective use of nasogastric decompression, larger multicenter trials are needed to establish definitive guidelines. Future research should focus on identifying specific risk factors and patient subgroups who might benefit from prophylactic nasogastric decompression.

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